

'PEROVSKIA KUDRJASCHEVII – A PROMISING SOURCE OF BIOLOGICALLY ACTIVE TERPENOIDS

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Relevance: *Perovskia kudrjashevii* Gorschk. & Pjataeva (family Lamiaceae) is a medicinal, essential oil, dye and honey plant. It is found in Uzbekistan, Tajikistan and Kyrgyzstan. The chemical composition of the components of *Perovskia kudrjashevii* has not been previously studied.

Purpose of the study. Isolation and study of biologically active components of the above-ground part and roots of *Perovskia kudrjashevii*, collected in the Bostandyk district of the Tashkent region.

Materials and methods. Crushed air-dried plant materials were extracted five times at room temperature with methanol. The combined extract was evaporated in vacuo, diluted with water and subjected to liquid-liquid extraction with benzene, chloroform, ethyl acetate and n-butanol.

Results. Two phenolic carboxylic acids, one diterpenoid and two phytosterols were isolated from different fractions of the methanol extract of the aerial parts by column chromatography on silica gel and Sephadex LH-20. Based on the study of UV, ¹H and ¹³C NMR spectra the isolated substances were identified with caffeic and rosmarinic acids, ferruginol, β-sitosterol and stigmasterol.

Fourteen individual compounds were isolated from the methanol extract of the roots by column chromatography on silica gel and Sephadex LH-20. Based on the study of UV, ¹H and ¹³C NMR spectra the isolated substances were identified with the bis-nor-diterpenoid przewalskin, nor-diterpenoids cryptotanshinone and tanshinone IIA, diterpenoids 7α-acetoxy-roileanone and sujiol, triterpenoids erythrodiol 3β-acetate, olean-12-ene-3β-O-acetyl-28-al, oleanolic acid and oleanolic acid 3-acetate. In addition to the above compounds, β-sitosterol, stigmasterol, caffeic and rosmarinic acids were isolated and identified from the roots. The spatial structure of 7α-acetoxyroileanone, erythrodiol 3β-acetate and olean-12-ene-3β-O-acetyl-28-al was established by X-ray diffraction analysis (XRD). The XRD materials of the above compounds were deposited at the Cambridge Crystallographic Data Centre.

All the isolated compounds have a diverse spectrum of pharmacological properties. Cryptotanshinone is characterized by anticancer, anti-inflammatory, immunoregulatory, neuroprotective and antifibrotic activity. Cryptotanshinone exhibits a pronounced anti-inflammatory effect in the experiment, suppressing both the exudative and proliferative phases of inflammation. In terms of the severity of its action, cryptotanshinone has shown certain advantages over diclofenac. Tanshinone IIA dilates coronary arteries and increases coronary blood flow due to the activation of potassium channels, has a cardioprotective and anti-inflammatory effect.

Conclusions. It has been shown that the *Perovskia kudrjashevii* plant is a rich source of biologically active phenolic carboxylic acids, diterpenoids, triterpenoids and can be used to create effective drugs and dietary supplements.